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Education Administration Using the New Normal and Quality Approach in the Suwannabhumi Prakarn Secondary School Consortium under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to 1) study the level of school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, 2) compare school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, classified by gender, age, education level, and work experience, and 3) gather suggestions, problems, and solutions for the development of school administration using these approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office. The sample group for the research consisted of 254 teachers from Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office. The research instruments used were questionnaires, with a reliability coefficient of 0.973, and interview forms. The statistics used for data analysis were the mean, standard deviation, and t-test. The finding revealed that: 1) The level of school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, was found to be high; 2) A comparison of school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, classified by gender, age, educational level, and work experience, showed no significant differences; 3) Regarding problem-solving guidelines for the development of school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, it was found that administrators, when making decisions, setting policies, or participating in planning, strive to allow personnel to express their views and participate in planning as much as possible. They ensure that their actions align with the context of each individual, the principles of correctness, and the policies and goals of the educational institution. Additionally, there is an emphasis on studying school data and analyzing key issues so that personnel, teachers, and students can gain a thorough understanding of the change process and the main driving factors for success.

Keywords: School Administration, New Approach, Quality Approach

1. Introduction

Quality and standardized education for the population is a crucial mechanism in driving national development. It also increases opportunities and equity in accessing education for all target groups of learners, which is essential in reducing inequality. The development of all educational institutions to achieve equal quality and standards, along with the establishment of support systems, encourages all capable and prepared sectors of society to participate in educational management. This includes creating a system to monitor key data related to educational institutions and learners, which is particularly important for institutions assisting children with special needs. Technology can be utilized to create equitable learning opportunities without limitations on format, time, or location. Reducing disparities in the quality and standards of educational institutions, promoting participation in educational management from all sectors, and encouraging the use of digital technology in education, as well as having accurate, complete, and up-to-date information systems, are all vital (National Education Plan 2017–2036: 119). This aligns with the National Education Act of 1999, Section 22, which states that education management should be based on the principle that every student can learn and grow, and students are the most important part of education. The method of education should help students perform their best and develop naturally and fully according to their potential, serving as a guideline for managing education to develop Thai people to keep up with the changes in today's world (Ministry of Education, 2007), especially in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The spread of COVID-19 has impacted education management worldwide, causing many institutions to close. As the pandemic affected many areas, the education system had to adapt to ensure learning continued, as this affected the quality of students. This led to changes in learning management, new innovations, and the emergence of new learning and teaching methods, transforming the way students learn. Educational institutions and various learning sources at all levels are needed to adapt to the current situation and prepare for future challenges (Thuean Thongkaew, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has directly impacted education. The Office of the Basic Education Commission is committed to developing basic education to become "New Normal Quality Education," focusing on ensuring safety in educational institutions, promoting equal opportunities for quality education, and managing education efficiently. The policies for the 2021-2022 fiscal years address educational safety by reducing risks for both students and staff in schools. In terms of opportunity, the focus is on ensuring that every preschool child has access to education, with good physical, mental, disciplinary, emotional, social, and intellectual development according to their age. Measures are in place to ensure that children and youth complete their basic education with quality and standards. There is also a system to support learners in basic education to prevent them from dropping out, and to assist those who do, ensuring they receive quality and equitable basic education. In terms of quality, the emphasis is on providing education that equips learners with knowledge, learning skills, and essential 21st-century skills, ensuring they are good, disciplined, love the nation's core institutions, and have the right attitude towards the country. Learners are developed with competence and skills in reading, mathematics, higher-order thinking, innovation, science, digital technology, and foreign languages. Teachers and educational personnel are developed to be modern, capable of delivering competency-based curriculum, skilled in their duties, knowledgeable in digital technology, and committed to continuous professional development, along with having the spirit of a teacher.

Regarding efficiency, the focus is on improving management systems, using area-based innovations as the primary mechanism driven by accurate and up-to-date information systems, and encouraging participation from all sectors. Schools are developed to sustain quality aligned with their local contexts. Educational opportunity expansion schools are managed to ensure students receive quality education, while specialized educational institutions and schools in special areas are supported. The area-based education innovation system is promoted as a model for educational innovation development, increasing flexibility in managing basic education (Amphon Pinasak, 2020).

The Secondary Education Service Area Office of Samut Prakan is an agency under the supervision of the Office of the Basic Education Commission, Ministry of Education. Its duty is to implement the Basic Education Commission's authority by bringing the policy of developing basic education into "New Normal Quality Education," in line with the objectives of the Secondary Education Service Area Office of Samut Prakan. The focus is on developing the quality of learners at all levels, expanding access to basic education services, ensuring all learners receive opportunities for full development according to their potential, and improving the quality of

teachers and educational personnel. The management system is improved by raising the quality of education management in the Secondary Education Service Area Office of Samut Prakan concretely. The ultimate goal is to ensure that students have access to quality education according to educational standards (Samut Prakan Secondary Education Service Area Office, 2022).

Given the aforementioned context and issues, the researcher is interested in conducting a study on "School Management Using the New Normal Quality Education Approach in Suvarnabhumi Prakan Network, Secondary Education Service Area Office of Samut Prakan" to develop school management that is prepared for the current society, aligned with the future, and helps promote and enhance school efficiency.

2. Research Objectives

1. Study the level of school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office,
2. Compare school administration using the new basic education and quality approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office, classified by gender, age, education level, and work experience, and
3. Gather suggestions, problems, and solutions for the development of school administration using these approaches in Suvarnabhumi Prakan, under the Samut Prakan Secondary Educational Service Area Office.

The research on " Education Administration Using the New Normal and Quality Approach in the Suwannabhumi Prakarn Secondary School Consortium under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan. " was conducted as follows:

2.1. Step 1: Study of Education Administration Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach

The research methodology for this study involved the following steps:

Target Group: The target group consisted of 254 teachers from schools within the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network, under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office Samut Prakan, for the academic year 2023.

Research Instrument: The research instrument was a questionnaire divided into two parts:

- Part 1: Questions on the demographic status of respondents (multiple choice).
- Part 2: A 5-point Likert scale questionnaire on school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach, covering four key areas.

The instrument development and validation process was as follows:

1. Review of related literature, theories, and previous studies on school management models.
2. Analysis of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach, which resulted in identifying four content areas.
3. Drafting of the questionnaire structure, divided into two sections.
4. Submission of the draft questionnaire to the research advisor for review, focusing on language accuracy, alignment with research objectives, and further suggestions for revisions.
5. Content validity testing of the questionnaire using the Index of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC) by three experts. All items had an IOC score between 0.60 and 1.00.
6. A try-out of the questionnaire was conducted with 30 teachers who were not part of the target group. The overall reliability of the questionnaire was calculated at .973.

Data Collection Method: A letter from the Faculty of Education and Liberal Arts at Suvarnabhumi Institute of Technology was sent to the school administrators within the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network to request permission to distribute the questionnaires. The questionnaires were collected on the appointed date. Upon return, the questionnaires were checked for completeness and correctness before being analyzed.

Data Analysis: All 254 questionnaires were returned, representing a 100% response rate. Data were analyzed using a computer program.

- Part 1 of the questionnaire was analyzed using frequency distribution and percentage.
- Part 2 of the questionnaire was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The rating scale interpretation was as follows:
 - Mean score between 4.51–5.00: Very high level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach.
 - Mean score between 3.51–4.50: High level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach.
 - Mean score between 2.51–3.50: Moderate level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach.
 - Mean score between 1.51–2.50: Low level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach.
 - Mean score between 1.00–1.50: Very low level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach.

2.2. Step 2: Suggestions and Solutions for Improving the New Normal Basic Education Quality Management

Informants: Three experts, selected based on their qualifications as school administrators, were from Bangpleeratrachbumrung School, Nawaminthrachinuthit Triamudomsuksapattanakarn School, and Pooncharoenwitthayakhom School.

Research Instrument: The research instrument was a structured interview, divided into two parts:

- Part 1: Demographic information of the experts.
- Part 2: Structured interview questions. The instrument development process included:
 1. Developing interview questions based on the lowest average scores from Step 1, resulting in 9 questions.
 2. Submitting the interview draft to the research advisor for review of language accuracy and content coverage, followed by necessary revisions and finalization.

Data Collection Method: Experts were personally contacted to arrange interviews and request their cooperation.

Data Analysis: The suggestions and solutions for improving the New Normal Basic Education Quality Management were analyzed and presented in essay form.

3. Research Findings Summary

Results of Data Analysis on Education Administration Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan:

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Education Administration Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan (Overall and by Aspect)

Item	Education Administration Using the New Normal and Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Secondary School Consortium under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan.	Management Level			
		$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Level	Rank
1.	Safety	4.16	.33	High	1
2.	Opportunity	4.14	.40	High	3
3.	Quality	4.16	.34	High	2
4.	Efficiency	4.13	.35	High	4
Total		4.14	.35	High	

(n= 254)

From Table 1, it was found that the school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, is at a high level overall ($M = 4.14$, $S.D. = .35$). When considered by individual aspects, it is also at a high level in all areas, ranked from highest to lowest mean scores as follows: Safety ($M = 4.16$, $S.D. = .33$) Quality ($M = 4.16$, $S.D. = .34$) Opportunity ($M = 4.14$, $S.D. = .40$) Efficiency ($M = 4.13$, $S.D. = .35$)

4. Research Findings

The research findings reveal the following:

1. **Data Analysis for Comparing School Management Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, Classified by Gender, Age, Educational Level, and Work Experience:**

2.1 **Comparison of School Management by Gender:** It was found that teachers of different genders have similar opinions regarding school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, both overall and in individual aspects.

2.2 **Comparison of School Management by Age:** It was found that teachers of different ages have similar opinions regarding school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, both overall and in individual aspects.

2.3 **Comparison of School Management by Educational Level:** It was found that teachers with different educational levels have similar opinions regarding school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, both overall and in individual aspects.

2.4 **Comparison of School Management by Work Experience:** It was found that teachers with varying work experience have similar opinions regarding school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, both overall and in individual aspects.

2. **Summary of Suggestions and Solutions for School Management Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan:**

The researcher compiled the results of the analysis by aspect and developed specific points for interviewing three administrators. The outcomes of the interviews with the school administrators are summarized as follows:

The schools in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network receive policies from the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan. Therefore, in decision-making or formulating certain policies, as well as in planning and operational practices, administrators strive to ensure that personnel can express their opinions and participate in planning to the greatest extent possible, suitable to the context of each individual while adhering to the principles of correctness. This is in line with the policies and goals of the educational institution. They study the school's data and analyze key issues to ensure that personnel, teachers, and students have knowledge and understanding of the processes of change and the main driving factors toward success. They provide training for personnel development, impart knowledge about school management, and serve as good role models to promote efficiency in all areas.

5. Discussion of Results

Objective 1: To study the level of school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan.

1. **Safety:** Overall and in each aspect, the level is high. This may be attributed to the administrators establishing committees and staff to monitor safety during operations in various school departments, as

well as providing security personnel for learning activities and organizing safety activities in the school. This is in line with the research conducted by Adisorn Deepanatham (2018), which studied the development of a participatory safety management model in schools under the Office of the Basic Education Commission. The findings showed that: 1) The current state of participatory safety management in schools is high overall; 2) The participatory safety management model comprises four aspects: (1) measures for preventing and resolving accidents in schools; (2) measures for preventing and addressing disasters in schools; (3) measures for preventing and addressing social issues; (4) measures for maintaining health security for students; 3) The participatory safety management model has been evaluated and endorsed by experts who participated in the second group discussion, confirming that the model is effective and can be applied in real situations.

2. **Opportunities:** Overall and in each aspect, the level is high. This may be because the administrators have developed a student support system in basic education and have opened opportunities for parents to participate in planning, supervising, monitoring, and evaluating to improve the student support system. This is consistent with the research conducted by Priyapat Srikhai and Thiraphat Thin San Dee (2022), which studied the management of student support systems in the New Normal era by school administrators at the Quality Development Center for Basic Education in Muang Sripheu, under the Primary Educational Service Area Office in Roi Et, District 2. The findings showed that: 1) The management of student support systems in the New Normal era is high overall; when considering each aspect, the ranking from highest to lowest average includes: screening, understanding individual students, prevention and resolution of issues, promotion and development, and referrals.
3. **Quality:** Overall and in each aspect, the level is high. This may be due to the administrators implementing policies to promote education that equips students with knowledge, learning skills, and essential 21st-century skills to enhance their competitiveness and choices for further education, while organizing practical learning processes. This aligns with the research conducted by Somsri Krenjathi (2017), which studied the school management model for developing student quality to possess desirable characteristics in the 21st century. The research found that, overall, the quality is high, with most aspects rated highly. The structural components included five aspects: the establishment of a management and organizational development system with participation from all sectors; the development of curricula and learning processes based on research; efficient resource and budget management; learning management that equips students with technological and communication competencies; and the development of information systems for resource and budget management, as well as promoting and supporting collaboration in academic development and learning resources, creating and providing media, innovations, and technology, and organizing integrated learning activities to develop 21st-century skills.
4. **Effectiveness:** Overall and in each aspect, the level is high. This may be because the administrators set policies and development plans that align with the school's curriculum and implement diverse management methods according to the school context. This corresponds with the research conducted by Natphat Boonket (2022), which studied the management of learning in the New Normal era of educational opportunity expansion schools under the Primary Educational Service Area Office in Sukhothai, District 2. The findings revealed six aspects: curriculum management, evaluation of learning outcomes in the New Normal, teaching and learning management, new resource management according to new priorities, teacher development, and listening to feedback from teachers, parents, students, and the community.

Objective 2: To compare the management of schools using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, classified by gender, age, educational level, and teaching experience.

From the research findings across all four areas, the results can be discussed as follows:

1. **Safety:** When classified by gender, age, educational level, and work experience, opinions on school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach showed no significant differences overall or in any specific area, which contradicts the hypothesis. This may be because teachers perceive that the administrators' approach to safety management is consistent. In the area of safety, administrators have implemented safety policies in schools and improved safety practices. This aligns with the research by Werasananing and Yuso (2011), which studied safety measures for students in primary schools under the Pattani Primary Educational Service Area Office 1. The findings revealed that: 1) Teachers with less

than 10 years of experience and those with 10 years or more did not differ significantly in their safety management practices across all six aspects; 2) Teachers in primary schools of different sizes showed no significant differences in safety management practices.

2. **Opportunities:** Classified by gender, age, educational level, and work experience, opinions on school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach showed no significant differences overall or in any specific area, which contradicts the hypothesis. This may indicate that teachers perceive the management of opportunities to be consistent across the board. In this area, administrators have implemented processes for screening students to promote educational equity and have encouraged activities that help students develop skills and qualities relevant to their career paths. This is consistent with research by Priyapat Sriksai and Thiraphat Thin San Dee (2022), which examined student support systems in the New Normal era. The findings indicated that teachers' opinions regarding individual student recognition and screening did not differ significantly based on gender, educational level, and work experience.
3. **Quality:** When classified by gender, age, educational level, and work experience, opinions regarding the management of schools using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach showed no significant differences overall or in specific areas, contradicting the hypothesis. Teachers likely view the quality management approach as consistent. In this regard, administrators promote education that provides students with the essential knowledge for the 21st century and establish management structures to develop students' multiple intelligences while encouraging teachers and students to learn about innovations in science and digital technology. This aligns with the research by Sunisa Sangadsri (2022), which studied the management skills of school leaders that impact the effectiveness of schools in the Sakon Nakhon Primary Educational Service Area Office 1. The research found that: 1) The management skills of administrators, as perceived by both school leaders and teachers, did not significantly differ based on school size; 2) The effectiveness of schools, according to both school leaders and teachers, showed no significant differences based on position status, school size, and work experience.
4. **Effectiveness:** When classified by gender, age, educational level, and work experience, opinions regarding the management of schools using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach showed no significant differences overall or in specific areas, contradicting the hypothesis. This may reflect teachers' perceptions of the consistency in how school leaders manage educational effectiveness. In terms of effectiveness, administrators establish policies and curricula that are efficiently managed and create cooperative networks with both public and private sectors for information exchange to facilitate learning. This aligns with research by Sunan Rung-Aornsangthong (2018), which studied the efficiency of basic education management. The findings revealed that effective basic education management comprises five components: 1) Management; 2) Quality academic management; 3) Financial and resource allocation management; 4) Promotion of personnel for quality work; 5) Community relationship management.

Objective 3: Problems and Solutions in School Management Using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan.

From the interviews, it was found that schools in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network follow policies from the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan. Therefore, when making decisions or formulating certain policies, as well as planning and implementing various practices, administrators strive to involve personnel in expressing opinions and participating in planning. They aim to ensure that everyone has a voice in alignment with the context of each individual while adhering to the principles of correctness and the policies and goals of the educational institution. There is a process of studying school data and analyzing key issues to ensure that personnel, teachers, and students understand the processes of change and the main driving factors for success. Training sessions are organized to develop staff, provide knowledge about school management and serve as role models to promote efficiency in all areas. This is consistent with research by Walaya Saetang and Thawisit Kunnapha (2023), which studied the quality management of new learning approaches in schools under the Bangkok Primary Educational Service Area Office. The findings revealed the following:

1. **Planning for the Development of New Learning Quality:**

- Schools plan to adapt the quality of their curriculum by setting standards, goals, and creating flexible school platforms suitable for new learning management.
 - Schools adjust the learning calendar, teaching schedules, and lesson plans to be flexible and appropriate for diverse new learning methods.
 - Schools plan to promote, support, and develop teachers in areas related to materials, equipment, and skills necessary for new learning management.
 - Schools plan to adapt the use of information technology systems in new learning management.
2. **Implementation of New Learning Quality Development:**
 - Schools adopt various methods for new learning management.
 - Administrators or designated individuals are responsible for modifying supervision, guidance, monitoring, and evaluating the new learning management process.
 3. **Monitoring and Evaluating the Quality Development of New Learning:**
 - Schools monitor the changes in evaluation methods for both teachers and students and provide support for students.
 4. **Improving and Modifying New Learning Quality Development:**
 - Schools lead in creating a positive attitude among all parties, with management and teachers collaboratively addressing issues that arise that do not align with the planned framework.

The research findings on the management quality of new learning in schools under the Bangkok Primary Educational Service Area Office can be utilized to enhance future management quality in new learning approaches.

6. Summary and Recommendations

The research on school management using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office, Samut Prakan, revealed that overall practices are at a high level, ranked from highest to lowest as follows: safety, quality, opportunity, and efficiency.

1. **Safety:** The area with the lowest average score is the promotion of activities that enhance students' mental well-being and instill values of love, unity, and mutual support. Therefore, administrators should emphasize the importance of public-mindedness among students as a crucial trait that should be nurtured and practiced within the school. Organizing activities that foster students' public-mindedness is essential for their learning and for enhancing their personal development.
2. **Quality:** The lowest average score is associated with administrators providing consultation and suggestions for instructional activities. Thus, administrators should take their responsibilities seriously, show enthusiasm for their duties, listen to feedback or problems from subordinates, and involve stakeholders in evaluating performance to facilitate quality development.
3. **Opportunity:** The area with the lowest average score is the promotion and development of quality education for students with disabilities. Therefore, administrators should increase access for teachers, students, parents, and the community to services. They should encourage students to express problems and significant approaches to the school's operations, ensuring that the institution treats all students equally without discrimination.
4. **Efficiency:** The lowest average score relates to administrators following up on the production of learning materials to encourage teachers to produce high-quality learning resources. Administrators should modernize their operational systems, integrating technology and various innovations into school management to reduce unnecessary and outdated workloads and effectively manage existing resources.

7. Recommendations for Utilizing Research Findings

1. **Study Factors Affecting School Management:** Investigate factors that influence the management of schools using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network. This will serve as a guideline for developing school management practices among administrators and cultivating a sense of responsibility in their work to achieve organizational goals efficiently.

2. **Examine Parental and Committee Perspectives:** Study the management of schools using the New Normal Basic Education Quality Approach in the Suvarnabhumi Prakarn Educational Network from the perspectives of parents or school committees. This can provide insights and feedback on school operations and enhance overall effectiveness.

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